

Nonlinear Equations with n-Dimensional Telegraph Operator Iterated K-Times

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Abstract : In this article, using distribution kernel, we study the nonlinear equations with n-dimensional telegraph operator iterated k-times.

Keywords : telegraph operator, elementary solution, distribution kernel, nonlinear equations

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